

GENDER CHARACTERISTICS AND THEIR ELIMINATION IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7251501>

Annotation: this article is about gender characteristics and methods of their elimination, which are found in children of preschool age, which is one of the most relevant issues of today.

Keywords: preschool education, children of preschool age, educator, gender, feminization, environment, temperament, gender, personality, audiovisual, informational, visual.

Education and upbringing of the younger generation, the formation of knowledge, skills, competencies in relation to the foundations of Science in them are considered the priority tasks of Public Policy. Especially in order to further improve the system of preschool education, to ensure equal use of pre-school education by children, to develop the non-state sector of preschool education services, as well as in the coming years the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 22, 2020 "on approval of the state standard of preschool education and education". From the main goals and objectives of resolution 802: -the organization of the system of preschool education based on modern requirements, raising children healthy and comprehensively mature, raising a spiritually harmonious generation, is defined as one of the priority tasks. In particular, if we talk about the work carried out in 2020 on Gender equality in the system of preschool education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, then in Uzbekistan at a time when the issue of ensuring Gender equality is of great importance around the world, this issue has been raised to the level of Public Policy and is a sign of the progressive. It is worth noting that in preschool educational organizations, gender characteristics are also differentiated in the behavior, timbre of the voice, and behavior of children.

Also, in February of this year, in cooperation with the Union of writers of the Republic, more than 50 scripts were created in preschool educational organizations within the framework of the circle of emeralds, in order to organize plot-role plays and other staged performances. These scenarios are rich in national values, cover our traditions, relationships between parents, children, a girl and a boy, situations aimed at the formation of gender equality in the minds of preschool children. By specialists of the Ministry of preschool education the

developed methodological recommendation" formation of gender equality in preschool institutions " is approved by the Coordination Council and is aimed at the educational and educational process.

In the same way,gender stability,gender characteristics of speech, gender differences between boys and girls are also found among schoolchildren of educational organizations.The role of gender in a child's life is also immeasurable.Gender education in preschool children is the formation in children of ideas about real men and women, and this is necessary for the normal and effective socialization of a person.Under the influence of educators and parents,a preschool child should study a sexual role or a gender model of a person's behavior so that he is a woman or identified as a man.

In order for your son or daughter to grow up and become a real man and woman,happily happy, you need to start raising them from childhood according to the gender principle.It should always be borne in mind that boys and girls are different hearing,sight,speaking and feeling from infancy.Girls are often obedient,while boys want to stand out;girls are more productive,while boys perceive information mainly through sight, and girls through the ear.You can continue to count the differences endlessly.

The teaching strategy used in kindergarten,forms and methods of working with children are often designed for girls.At the same time ,girls and boys are often brought up by women at home-mother or grandmother, and in kindergarten-a female educator.As a result, gender tolerance for many boys is formed without the participation of men.And women,according to scientists,cannot raise boys correctly, only for one simple reason:they have a different type of brain and a different type of thinking.In addition,female traininghci naturally, preschool boys do not have the childhood experience of the experiences that they encounter when communicating with adults and with children.Therefore,when communicating with boys, many teachers adhere to the idea that if this is a boy,then again, in uiro,strength is a symbol of endurance.As a result,not at all courageous, but scary physically weak and very weak boys are regularly exposed to the traumatic effects of teachers.

In conclusion, the more correctly the educational process is organized, the more discordant in the upbringing of children who are brought up in the mask, as well as in their behavior, and irregular movements do not cause psychological complications.

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